

Review on Negative Symptoms of Schizophrenia

A Comprehensive Overview of Etiology, Risk Factors, and Treatment Approaches in Schizophrenia

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Abstract

Background: Schizophrenia encompasses a syndrome of disorders that are chronic in nature. It is characterized by a combination of symptoms such as delusions, hallucinations, abnormal mental processes, disordered communication, disordered conceptualization, and negative symptoms. This study reviews negative symptoms such as apathy, avolition, blunting, and asociality, and their clinical significance in the prognosis of schizophrenia.

Methods: Primary negative symptoms were reviewed as idiopathic to the pathophysiology of schizophrenia, while secondary negative symptoms were associated with the environment, medications, and other factors. Data were gathered from prior studies and classified accordingly.

Results: Findings indicate a significant correlation between chronic negative symptoms and poor social and occupational functioning. Primary negative symptoms remain persistent, even during times of clinical stability, and are difficult to treat.

Conclusion: Negative symptoms play a significant role in schizophrenia, and there is a need for further research and treatment options.

Keywords: Negative symptoms, schizophrenia, avolition, primary symptoms

INTRODUCTION

In 1980, Crow coined dichotomies of schizophrenia, which were modified in 1985, in which Bleuler and Haslam were considered as forefathers [1]. Schizophrenia encompasses a syndrome of disorders that are chronic in their course and disabling in nature. It is characterised by a combination of symptoms such as delusions, hallucinations, abnormal mental processes, disordered communication, disordered conceptualization, disordered behaviour, poor planning, disruption in the affective domains, and a decrease in motivation.

The main focus of this review is on negative symptoms, which include apathy, blunting or inconsistent emotional reactions, avolition and lack of motivation, paucity of speech, attention deficit disorder, and asociality. Because of the enormous social and economic consequences, including indirect expenses like the loss of the patient's and, in some situations, the caregiver's livelihood due to unemployment, carers endure significant distress secondary to the patient's unpleasant symptoms. Different categories have been used to group negative symptoms. Negative symptoms were divided into primary and secondary negative symptoms in the 1980s.

PRIMARY NEGATIVE SYMPTOMS

Primary negative symptoms, also known as deficiency syndrome or idiopathic negative symptoms, are thought to be etiologically connected to the basic pathophysiology seen in schizophrenia. This particular combination of symptoms is thought to be persistent in nature and to remain even during times of clinical stability [2].

SECONDARY NEGATIVE SYMPTOMS

Comparatively, the secondary negative symptoms are thought to be a derivative of the prescribed drugs, additional co-occurring disease processes, or the environment. For instance, secondary to extrapyramidal symptoms, blunted affect, and akinesia that have developed as a result of taking anti-psychotic medications. These symptoms typically respond well to treatment [3]. According to prior studies, the prevalence of deficit syndrome was believed to be between 25% and 30% in people with persistent schizophrenia and to be around 15% in those experiencing their first episode of psychosis. One or more of the negative symptoms appeared to be present in 57.6% of patients, according to a large cross-sectional study involving 1,452 patients [3]. The most prevalent negative symptoms were social withdrawal, poor rapport, emotional withdrawal, muted affect, and poor rapport. In another study, 41% of the approximately 7678 patients with a schizophrenia diagnosis were found to exhibit two or more of the negative symptoms [4].

NOSOLOGY DIFFERENCE

In DSM5 and 5TR diagnosis of schizophrenia, 'A' criteria included negative symptoms. In ICD-10 diagnosis of schizophrenia, 'h' criteria included negative symptoms. In ICD-11 diagnosis of schizophrenia, 'e' criteria included negative symptoms. In all the above diagnostic systems, negative symptoms are not given priority and are not a must criteria but their impact on prognosis is accountable. Hence, their weightage is more when it comes to the course and prognosis of illness than diagnosis [5,6].

RISK FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH NEGATIVE SYMPTOMS IN SCHIZOPHRENIA

Males scored more negatively than females, which is a pattern that has been previously observed. Those without a job scored higher than stay-at-home moms and people with other jobs. Higher marks were awarded to individuals who had given up working and those who had never held a job that paid a living wage. Positive symptom scores were greater among people who had stopped working because of illness or medication side effects. This is comparable to past research that found that patients who were employed were less likely than those who were unemployed to experience negative symptoms. People who are currently unmarried (never married, divorced, or separated) had higher ratings that tended to be significant. According to other studies, single people are more likely to experience unfavourable symptoms. The prevalence of debt and a negative correlation between household income and the negative symptom score were likely secondary effects of dysfunction and unemployment. Clinical factors included fair or poor drug compliance, a continuous course of illness, and significantly higher SANS, indicating that chronic illness and insufficient treatment may influence negative symptoms. There was no correlation between the number of admissions and age, increased familial risk of schizophrenia, season of birth, antipsychotic dosage, or age. The relationship between outcome and linguistic proficiency in negative schizophrenics was shown to be positive. Low linguistic competence in a person with negative schizophrenia results in high levels of negative symptoms that are difficult to treat.

DEFINITIONS OF NEGATIVE SYMPTOMS

Avolition

It is the inability or difficulty of starting and maintaining goal-directed behaviour. It is frequently misinterpreted for outward disinterest. The individual may not feel inspired to pursue objectives and activities. They might not feel like they have much of a purpose in life and may not have many interests. They could experience fatigue or drowsiness and struggle to carry out even straightforward plans.

Anhedonia

The inability to enjoy activities that one used to find pleasurable.

Affective Flattening

It is characterised by a decrease in the range of emotional expressiveness, which includes a limited or unresponsive range of facial expression, poor eye contact, and diminished body language. The person's facial expression, vocal tone, and gesticulation range may be limited or diminished. This does not imply that the person is not feeling or responding to his or her surroundings, though.

Alogia

It is also known as speech poverty, is a reduction in the fluency and production of speech. The subject may have trouble speaking or be mute, and they may respond to questions with brief, meaningless statements [7].

NEUROBIOLOGY AND PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

Negative symptoms are associated with certain pathophysiological mechanisms that have not yet been firmly identified. Hughlings Jackson proposed nearly 150 years ago that the positive symptoms actually reflect a loss of the higher inhibitory controls that causes the excitation or release of the lower systems, as opposed to the negative symptoms, which actually reflect a dissolution and loss of function of the "neural arrangements." Studies have looked into the potential relationship between unpleasant symptoms and other biological factors such as platelet monoamine oxidase as well as the ventricular enlargement shown on computed tomography imaging. Recent research suggests that negative symptoms are likely caused by disruption in the fronto-cortico-temporal networks. Other research has suggested that additional brain regions, including the parietal and insular cortices, the thalamus, and the amygdala, may be involved. Studies also point to a potential alteration in the GABAergic-glutamatergic balance, dopaminergic neuron signalling, and transmission along the oxytocinergic and cannabinoidergic pathways at the cellular level. The findings so far have been inconsistent and mixed [8].

Dopamine D3 receptors may be involved in the modulation of negative symptoms, mood, and cognition since they are found in mesolimbic areas of the brain that regulate reward, emotion, and motivation. Results from animal models have suggested that antagonism and partial agonism at dopamine D3 receptors can mediate enhancements in social interaction, novel object recognition, as well as displaying D3-receptor-mediated anti-anhedonic and procognitive effects in rodents. These findings have provided evidence in support of this hypothesis [9]. The exact mechanism by which these effects might take place is unknown, but it is possible that D3 receptor antagonists in the midbrain (such as the ventral tegmental area) could increase dopamine neurotransmission to the prefrontal cortex and the nucleus accumbens, two regions of the brain where low levels of dopamine have been linked to unpleasant symptoms and mood deficits [10]. Increased D1 receptor activation due to this normalisation of dopamine release in the prefrontal cortex may facilitate improvements in cognition and negative symptoms [11]. Additionally, D3 receptors have been linked to altered glutamatergic excitability, increased acetylcholine release in the prefrontal cortex, and control over dopamine, CREB phosphorylation, and gamma oscillations in the hippocampus, all of which have the potential to modulate schizophrenia-related cognitive and/or mood symptoms [12].

Although several studies have found that drugs that act at the NMDA receptor's glycine accessory site (such as D-cycloserine) facilitate glutamate neurotransmission and increase the effectiveness of antipsychotic medications, particularly when used to treat the disease's negative symptoms, the evidence is conflicting [13].

Avolition neurobiology

An important aspect of schizophrenia's negative symptoms is effort-based decision making, which is easily measured in both people and rodents. Also found are subdomains whose brain mechanisms can be studied in mouse research. Dopamine D2 receptors contribute to physical effort and reward-associative learning, whereas dopamine D1 receptors have been linked to every facet of decision making. 7 nicotinic acetylcholine receptors and cannabinoid CB1 receptors have both been linked to reward-associative learning, and CB1 receptors may also be responsible for cognitive effortful motivation [14].

Anhedonia neurobiology

Patients with schizophrenia have normal levels of enjoyment when immediately engaged in a pleasurable action, or consummatory pleasure, but have abnormalities in their enjoyment of pleasure associated with upcoming activities, or anticipatory pleasure. These hedonic experience components have distinct brain architecture, neurotransmitter involvement, and behavioural aftereffects. While serotonergic and opioid systems appear to play a more prominent role in consummatory pleasure, anticipatory pleasure appears to heavily, though not solely, rely on dopamine and the mesolimbic pathway [15].

Affective flattening neurobiology

Most studies reveal that patients exhibit under-recruitment compared to controls in the amygdala, hippocampus, fusiform gyrus, and anterior cingulate gyrus, which are all involved in processing affect. On the other hand, current research suggests that the amygdala is over-recruited. Negative Symptom like blunted affect predominate in childhood and early-onset schizophrenia [16].

INSTRUMENTS FOR ASSESSMENT OF NEGATIVE SYMPTOMS

A combination of direct observation and questions about the person's daily activities and interactions with others make up the tools used for the assessments of unpleasant symptoms. Early in the 1980s, Nancy Andreasen developed the Scale for the Assessment of Negative Symptoms (SANS), which is now regarded as the gold standard for evaluating negative symptoms in schizophrenia. The Clinical Global Impression scale (CGI), the Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS), the Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS), the 16-item Negative Symptoms Assessment (NSA-16), the Schedule for Deficit Syndrome (SDS), the Clinical Assessment Interview for Negative Symptoms (CAINS), and the Brief Negative Symptoms Scale (BNSS) are additional tools that can be used to evaluate negative symptoms in schizophrenia [17].

ASSESSMENT BEYOND RATING SCALE

Positive symptom management and timely and accurate assessment are essential components of providing quality patient care. Clinicians must rely on observations made during the interview, feedback from informants, and information gathered through revealing questions because some patients may have limited self-awareness of negative symptoms as a part of their illness. A careful evaluation of the patient's responses to questions can help rule out other diseases (such as concomitant depression), which are common in patients with schizophrenia-spectrum disorders, or it can assist evaluate whether a diagnosis other than negative symptoms is applicable. The responses to queries like "What kind of mood are you in?" or "How do you feel today?" can aid a therapist in assessing a patient's affect and may offer significant correlates to vocal tonality, gestures, and facial expressions when analysing the emotional expression.

In order to determine a patient's ability to expound on a response without prompting, if they engage in enjoyable activities to test for anhedonia, have social contacts to test for social drive, and are goal-oriented and productive, questions should be worded to elicit a range of answers. How do you spend a normal day? and similar inquiries are more instances of queries that can elicit interesting answers. What activities do you enjoy? Have you recently had the chance to interact with folks who aren't members of your family? Moreover, do you wish you had a job? The patient should be encouraged to communicate further by following up with questions like "Tell me about that" or "What would be a good first step to get a job?".

Some essential indications, such poor grooming and hygiene, diminished or impoverished speech content, and other behaviours, can only be seen in patients with more severe negative symptoms. Future developments in the management of schizophrenia generally, and negative symptoms in particular, are anticipated to make it easier to access and use data gathered through digital technology, such as smartphone applications like HORYZONS AND SCORES. Clinicians may benefit from using technologies to monitor negative symptoms in outpatients, avoid relapse, promote drug adherence, provide real-time support, promote physical activity, and broaden access to services [18].

As a result, doctors must be on the lookout for any unfavourable symptoms that are clinically pertinent in order to treat them effectively and enhance patient outcomes. Given that the majority of schizophrenia patients may have noticeable negative symptoms, a personalised medicine approach is encouraged, in which the patient's particular symptom profile is taken into account when treating them. By observing their behaviour, interviewing them and their family members or friends, giving a formal assessment like the NSA-4, taking into account alternative medical diagnoses, and addressing factors that are connected to secondary negative symptoms, clinicians can give each patient the most effective treatment [19].

STUDIES FROM INDIA

Only a small number of studies conducted in India have focused on the negative symptoms of the schizophrenia psychiatric condition. According to one study, the negative symptoms were observed to be more stable than the positive symptoms. Another study discovered that individuals with schizophrenia who were mildly depressed also appeared to have retained insight and had lower negative symptom scores [20].

PERSISTENT NEGATIVE SYMPTOMS CRITERIA

The negative symptoms of schizophrenia that are

1. Primary to the condition are among the persistent negative symptoms.
2. May be secondary, yet the standard treatments for these symptoms have not worked for them.
3. Make it difficult for the patient to carry out regular job duties
4. Continue throughout times of clinical stability
5. Exhibit an unfulfilled therapeutic demand [19].

Proposed Negative Symptom Terminology

- *Negative symptoms*- Broadly defined as a reduction of normal functions either related to motivation and interest (eg, avolition, anhedonia, and asociality) or to expressive functions (eg, blunted affect and alogia)
- *Deficit syndrome* -A symptom complex characterized by primary and enduring negative symptoms that are present for most of the preceding 12 months (including during periods of clinical stability); they are caused by a specific disease process that is separate from the genetic and neurobiological factors that contribute to nondeficit schizophrenia
- *Predominant negative symptoms*- Clinically relevant negative symptoms of greater relative severity than co-occurring positive symptoms; no duration is specified so symptoms could be present for a relatively short time period or they could be long-standing
- *Prominent negative symptoms*- Pronounced and clinically relevant negative symptoms of unspecified duration; reflects the clinical reality of most patients whose illness does not have a clear prominence of either positive or negative symptoms [21].
- *Primary negative symptoms*- Negative symptoms that are thought to be intrinsic to the underlying pathophysiology of schizophrenia
- *Secondary negative symptoms*- Negative symptoms that are thought to be related to other factors, such as psychiatric or medical comorbidities, treatment adverse effects, or environmental factors
- *Persistent (enduring) negative symptoms*- Primary negative symptoms or secondary negative symptoms that have not responded to treatment for a minimum of 6 months, interfere with normal role functioning, and persist during periods of clinical stability [22].

EXPLANATORY MODELS

Explanatory model is one which tends to reveal how people try and make sense of the illness and the experiences they are having.

BEMI: The Bart Explanatory Model Inventory was developed by a researcher who identified a gap in culturally varied beliefs assessed by other instruments

EMIC: The Explanatory Model Interview Catalogue is a semi - structured interview that was made in an attempt to help better integrate the clinical, social science and epidemiological aspects

One hypothesises that divide the illness's causes into categories of the natural and supernatural. Organic degeneration, infection, accident, stress, and overt aggressiveness were all included in the natural category. In contrast, the supernatural category included the esoteric, magical, and animistic sources of disease [23].

COGNITIVE MODEL OF NEGATIVE SYMPTOMS IN SCHIZOPHRENIA

Some evidence suggests that neurocognitive deficits in schizophrenia can result in failure experiences or failure expectations, which can affect a person's daily functioning and result in dysfunctional, asocial attitudes and a negative evaluation of their self and potentials (for example, "If I don't do well all the time, people won't respect me" or "If I fail partially, it's as if I failed completely"). Negative symptoms could result from dysfunctional and antisocial attitudes. Apathy, indifference, withdrawal from social relationships, lack of engagement in purposeful actions, and interference are examples of cognitive model of negative symptoms. The hypothesis that negative symptoms act as an unhelpful defence against the pain and rejection that are expected when engaging in constructive activities. Furthermore, the issue is made worse by beliefs brought on by the stigma associated with mental illness, such as "I won't be able to achieve anything or have meaningful relationships because I have schizophrenia [24]."

NEGATIVE SYMPTOM COURSE

Despite the fact that they typically do not serve as the basis for patients' initial requests for clinical care, negative symptoms have been documented to be among the most prevalent initial symptoms of schizophrenia. Early negative symptoms in psychotic diseases may begin and evolve as a result of genetic influences, prenatal circumstances, and inadequate premorbid adjustment [25]. Negative symptoms frequently manifest during schizophrenia's prodromal stage and prior to the first acute psychotic episode. Negative symptoms were experienced by patients in 20% of cases during the same month as positive symptoms and 73% of cases prior to the commencement of positive symptoms. A risk factor for the transition to psychosis and prodromal emergence of negative symptoms is linked to negative symptoms in the initial psychotic episode. Clinicians should be aware of positive symptoms that are accompanied by diminished emotional expression, social disengagement, and functional decline because negative symptoms can also appear during the psychotic phase of illness. Negative symptoms have an ambiguous long-term trajectory, with some research indicating that they are rather stable over time while others suggest that they may fluctuate or be reversible. The distribution of positive versus negative or mixed presentations is also ambiguous and may vary between samples [26]. Negative symptoms are frequent and can appear at any time during the course of the illness; for instance, up to 90% of patients experiencing their first psychotic episode reported at least one negative symptom, and 35-70% of patients continued to experience clinically significant negative symptoms even after receiving treatment. In routine clinical practise, 61% of stable outpatients with schizophrenia who were receiving antipsychotic treatment were found to have at least 1 negative symptom of moderate severity or worse. The most prevalent symptoms included social disengagement (48%), emotional withdrawal (42%), and impaired rapport (39%), while 19% of patients had all 5 unfavourable symptoms [27].

PROGNOSIS

The prognosis of the illness depends on the presence of negative symptoms. They are reported to dramatically worsen cognitive deficiencies, worsen work performance, impede social functioning, and ultimately have a worse prognosis. They are known to worsen the severity of the illness.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS

Although negative symptoms are typically associated with schizophrenia, they can also be found in other diseases. In order to provide effective treatment, clinicians must rule out other medical (such as multiple sclerosis, Parkinson's disease) or psychiatric (such as depression, anxiety, obsessive-compulsive disorder, posttraumatic stress disorder, autism, intellectual disability, substance abuse) conditions that may present with negative symptoms. It is essential to rule out above differential diagnosis rather than mislabelling negative symptoms as depression and catatonia [28].

PHARMACOLOGICAL TREATMENT

The mainstay of treatment for acute psychotic episodes is antipsychotic medication, which, on average, improves symptoms of schizophrenia in 81% of patients with first episode schizophrenia and in 51% of people with chronic schizophrenia [29]. Antipsychotic drugs also decreased the likelihood of psychotic relapses after 7–12 months after an acute episode had ended. The majority of currently available medications, however, have negligible effects on negative symptoms of schizophrenia that are not related to positive symptoms, and the FDA has not yet approved any medication to treat negative symptoms. The majority of reports of improvement in negative symptoms are based on short-term trials in patients with concomitant negative symptoms and acute psychotic disease. Few research have been prospectively planned to investigate the effect of treatment on persistent negative symptoms. As a result, it is challenging to discern whether changes in negative symptoms in the majority of reported trials are a true result of treatment or a result of improvements in other symptom categories (such as positive, depressive, or extrapyramidal symptoms), and there is a dearth of long-term data [30]. In a meta-analysis of antipsychotic medication studies that were blinded, randomised, and conducted on people with schizophrenia, the only antipsychotic that was superior to placebo in the treatment of predominant negative symptoms was low-dose amisulpride, which is approved for the treatment of negative symptoms in a small number of European countries. However, a parallel reduction in depression was also noticed, making it difficult to determine whether the reduction in negative symptoms was a result of improvement in depression [31].

As of now, a meticulously planned 26-week study comparing the effects of fixed-dose cariprazine (3 mg/d, 4.5 mg/d [target dose], or 6 mg/d) and risperidone (3 mg/d, 4 mg/d [target dose], or 6 mg/d) on predominate negative symptoms in patients with stable and limited positive symptoms is the only prospective, large-scale, randomised, double-blind evidence demonstrating the superiority of one approved antipsychotic [32].

The purpose of this study was to investigate whether cariprazine, a dopamine D3-preferring D3/D2 receptor partial agonist and a serotonin 5-HT1A receptor partial agonist, is superior to a D2-preferring antagonist in treating negative symptoms and cognition in schizophrenia patients. Furthermore, superiority in terms of the improvement of negative symptoms was also accompanied by significant advantages for cariprazine over risperidone on the Clinical Global Impressions-Improvement Scale and the Personal and Social Performance Scale, showing that the improvement of the negative symptoms with cariprazine also resulted in clinically significant advantages [33].

Other medications have been used in conjunction with antipsychotics to address negative symptoms in addition to antipsychotic monotherapy. For other adjunctive medications, such as minocycline, dopamine agonists (such as selegiline, modafinil), cholinergics (such as galantamine, donepezil), glutamatergic compounds (such as glycine, D-serine, and D-cycloserine), there is only weak evidence against side effects. Additionally, some study has been done on repurposed medications (such as minocycline, oestrogen, raloxifene, and folate), but the lack of financial incentives makes it difficult to sponsor treatment trials for medications that have previously received approval for use in other situations, are generic, or are available over-the-counter. At this time, there is insufficient data to propose any specific cotreatment strategy for the treatment of schizophrenia patients [34]. L carnosine around 800mg to 2gm is found to be effective in improving negative and cognitive symptoms [35].

Drug development is ongoing in this therapeutic field for medicines with activity at several receptors, including NMDA receptors, alpha 7 nicotinic receptors, 5-HT2A and sigma-2 receptors, given the significant unmet medical need associated with negative sensations. Notably, a phase 2b experiment found that roluperidone (MIN-101), an antagonist at both sigma-2 and 5-HT2A receptors without direct dopamine affinities, significantly reduced negative symptoms compared to placebo in stable patients with schizophrenia. Additionally, meta-analyses have demonstrated that antidepressants such as mirtazapine and mianserin might be useful in relieving negative symptoms. Additionally, several medical devices that employ techniques like transcranial direct current stimulation and deep transcranial magnetic stimulation are being researched [36].

COGNITIVE AND NEGATIVE SYMPTOMS IN SCHIZOPHRENIA TRIAL (CONSIST)

A 16-week, double-blind, double-dummy, parallel group, randomised clinical trial of adjunctive glycine, D-cycloserine, or placebo was done at four sites in the United States and one site in Israel as part of the Cognitive and Negative Symptoms in Schizophrenia Trial (CONSIST). 157 inpatients and outpatients who satisfied the DSM-IV criteria for schizophrenia or schizoaffective disorder as well as retrospective and prospective criteria for moderate to severe negative symptoms without noticeable positive, depressed, or extrapyramidal symptoms made up the participants. The change in average cognitive domain z scores and the average "rate of change" of Scale for the Assessment of Negative Symptoms (SANS) total scores were the key end measures. According to the study's findings, glycine and D-cycloserine are neither typically useful therapeutic agents for treating adverse symptoms or cognitive deficits [37].

PSYCHOSOCIAL INTERVENTIONS

CBT, or cognitive behavioural therapy, is a well-known and successful transdiagnostic approach. According to the cognitive paradigm, how we perceive events affects how we think, feel, and act; these interpretations then work to establish and maintain undesirable reactions. CBT has a wide range of objectives, including the reduction of specific symptoms, better comprehension of the condition, lowering of distress, and the development of adaptable coping mechanisms. A clinically meaningful decrease in negative symptoms was demonstrated by 35% of CBT participants at the one-year (i.e., a reliable improvement), while just over half (55%) were classified as belonging to the healthy population, indicating a modest benefit. Social skill training is one of the psychosocial treatments and the purpose of Social Skills Training is to assist individuals in developing the necessary skills to become socially competent. Social competence is improved by a specific set of components, such as expressive, receptive, and conversational skills, as well as any additional elements that may have an impact on an individual's capacity for social interaction (e.g., assertiveness skills, situational elements, independent living abilities, and medication management). Expressive behaviour is improved by specific set of components such as nonverbal behaviours like appropriate facial expression, eye contact, body language, and proxemics, as well as verbal behaviours such as appropriate verbal content, form, structure, appropriate vocabulary, and quantity of speech. Receptive behaviour is improved by specific set of components include the capacity to pay attention to the person you are conversing with (including listening, clarifying, relevant, and timeliness), as well as the capacity to perceive emotions. Adding a social component to Cognitive Remediation Training (such as group format, problem-solving, or social cognitive skills) may be beneficial for reducing unpleasant symptoms [38].

CONCLUSION

In order to enhance patient outcomes, negative symptoms of schizophrenia, which are present in the majority of patients, must be identified, assessed, and managed as effectively as feasible. Negative symptoms are more closely related to poor patient functioning, a worse quality of life, and decreased productivity than positive symptoms, which can be better addressed by available treatment options. This is because negative symptoms are frequently not recognised by clinicians and there are few evidence-based treatments available. Positive results have been obtained by developing drugs that target undesirable symptoms.

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